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Jamila Damirova Vagif

PhD in Philology

National Museum of Azerbaijani Literature named after Nizami Ganjavi

Head of the Department of Doctoral Studies and Scientific Development

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LONGING FOR HOMETLAND AND SICILIAN MOTIFS IN THE POETRY OF IBN HAMDIS

Abstract:

The most prominent representative of Arab-Sicilian literature is Ibn Hamdis. Although the poet left Sicily at a young age, motifs related to his homeland formed the main direction of his rich creative work. Whether during his years at the Abbadid court in al-Andalus or while living in the Maghreb, he repeatedly referred to Sicily. His poems on this subject are known as *as-Siqilliyyāt* (□□□□□□□□). Many genres of Arabic poetry—such as panegyric (*madīh*), elegy (*marthiyya*), description (*wasf*), wisdom poetry (*ḥikma*), and love poetry (*ghazal*)—enabled him to express his longing for Sicily. In Ibn Hamdis' poetry, several issues characteristic of Arab-Muslim society are reflected, such as the conflict and bloody strife of the "Mulūk al-Ṭawā'if" (□□□□ □□□□□□□□ – Taifa kings) period, calls for unity against the Reconquista, and the anxiety and pessimism in the face of growing Christian attacks. Alongside these themes, Ibn Hamdis was also a magnificent poet of love and affection. In his poetry, the *ghazal* genre is closely intertwined with *khamriyya* (wine poetry). A zest for life forms the main thread of these two genres, as well as of descriptive poetry. The themes of youth and old age often bring back memories of his homeland, Sicily, and in his later years, the poet fondly recalls the happy days of his youth with a special sense of pleasure.

Keywords: Sicilian literature, Sicily under Arab rule, Ibn Hamdis' poetry, *Siqilliyyāt*, Arabo-Islamic literature and culture

Introduction: The geographical scope of Ibn Hamdis' literary work is quite extensive. After leaving Sicily and traveling to al-Andalus, the poet then heads to North Africa. Seeking refuge under the patronage of rulers established in North Africa, he composes eulogies in their honor. N. Carpentieri notes that Ibn Hamdis travels to Mahdia in North Africa and turns to the Zirid court. There, he praises members of the Zirid dynasty, including Tamim ibn al-Mu'izz (1062–1108), Yahya ibn Tamim (1108–1131), Ali ibn Yahya (1115–1121), and his son Hasan ibn Ali (1121–1152) (Carpentieri, 2016). He also writes panegyrics for Mansur ibn al-Nasir, the head of the Hammadid dynasty in Béjaïa. Toward the end of his life, Ibn Hamdis dedicates two eulogies to Emir Nasir ad-Dawla in Mallorca (Carpentieri, 2016). This period of Ibn Hamdis' poetry is not limited to panegyrics alone. He also experiments with other genres such as elegy (*marthiya*), ascetic poetry (*zuhdiyyah*), wine poetry (*khamriyyah*), and descriptive verse (*wasf*).

The longing for Sicily in Ibn Hamdis' work permeates poems written in various genres. The poet repeatedly revisits this theme in panegyrics addressed to different emirs while in exile, in elegies dedicated to compatriots who passed away far from home, and in poems depicting old age.

1. The Genre Diversity of Ibn Hamdis's Poems on Longing for the Homeland

One such poem is a panegyric composed by Ibn Hamdis in honor of Tamim ibn al-Mu'izz, the Zirid ruler of Mahdia. In this panegyric, the poet expresses his sorrow over the fall of Muslim rule in Sicily at the

hands of the Normans. The *qasida* begins on a mournful note; the poet invokes the motif of *dahr* (time/fate) and laments the injustices of the age. Employing the rhetorical device of *iltifāt*, he occasionally addresses himself in the second person:

فإن لم تُسألَمْ تَدْرَعْتُ صِيرِي جُنَّةً لِلنَّوَانِبِ
يا زمان فحارب عجمت حصاةً لا تَلين لعاجِمِ
ورضت شموساً لا يَنل لراكِبِ

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

I clothed myself in patience like armor in the face of misfortunes.

O Time! If you are not inclined toward peace, then hurl yourself into battle.

You have dared to bite into stones that cannot be digested!

You have tamed a wild steed that no rider could ever mount."

The poet conveys the bitterness of exile, lamenting his deprivation of the blessings he once enjoyed in Sicily.

فطمت بها عن كل كأس ولذة (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

"I was cut off in exile from every delightful cup and pleasure."

In the following verses, the influence of al-Mutanabbī is discernible. Al-Mutanabbī, too, spent part of his life in exile—at the court of Kāfūr, the Ikhshidid ruler of Egypt. Upon leaving Egypt, the poet composed a scathing satire against Kāfūr. In that invective, he declares that he no longer inclines toward the sword, but rather embraces girls with graceful necks.

This notion opens a different thematic path in Ibn Hamdis's poem. Unlike al-Mutanabbī, Ibn Hamdis

does not favor beautiful women; instead, he prioritizes the sword.

بيت رئاس العضب في ثني ساعدي من معاوذة
 جيد غيداء كاعب وما ضاحخ الهندي إلا مثلماً
 الوغى في الضرائب مضاربه يوم
 إذا كان لي في السيف أنس ألفتة
 فلا وحشة عندي لفقد الحبايب
 فكنت، وقدّي في الصبا مثل قدّه،
 عهدت إليه أن منه مكاسبي
 (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

I no longer embrace beautiful girls, but instead carry a sword at my side.

From the blows I struck on the day of battle, the tip of my sword became notched and jagged.

I would sleep embracing such a sword.

Because of my friendship with the sword,

I no longer feared being separated from my beloved.

Both my youth and my stature were as straight as a sword, and in those days, I vowed that even my fate in life would be forged of steel.

In these verses, the poet employs literary devices such as **simile** (comparing his stature to a sword), **metaphor** (embracing the sword as though it were a beloved), and **hyperbole** (the sword's edge being fragmented). These couplets, infused with a tone of **pride and self-praise (fakhriyyah)**, suggest that the poet was no stranger to warfare in his youth—he girded himself with a sword and entered battle. During that period, tribal rulers fought among themselves and also faced attacks from the Normans in the north. The specific battles or opponents in which the poet participated remain unknown.

Later, the poet speaks of withdrawing from the malice of people and living a life of exile, where each passing month feels as long as a century. He describes Sicily as a shining star in his sky. Having lived far from his homeland for a long time, the poet has become accustomed to a life in exile. Even his speech has acquired strange and unfamiliar words as a result.

ولي في سماء الشرق مطلع كوكب من جلا
 طلوعي بين زهر الكواكب
 ألفت اغترابي عنه حتى تكاثرت
 له عقد الأيام في كفت حاسب
 متى تسمع الجوزاء في الجو منطقي في
 مقالي لارتجال الغرائب
 (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

*A star of mine has risen in the sky of the East,
 And this star shines brightly among the others.*

As I knot each passing day onto a string,

These days have stretched on so long

That I have grown accustomed to the life of exile.

If the constellation Gemini were to hear my speech in the sky,

It would need to clarify the strange words

That I spontaneously utter in my exile-born language.

In his *madihiyyah* (panegyric), the poet describes his days as joyful. His nights seem adorned with pearls and gems, so radiant that he has no need to look upon the shining moon in the sky—for Tamim himself is the "moon of virtue." The poet wistfully remarks that if

only the rulers of Sicily in the past had been like him, his homeland might have been free, and he could have returned whenever he wished.

لو أنّ أرضي خرةً لا تبيها يعزّم بعد السير ضربةً
 لأزب ولكن أرضي كيف لي بفكاكها من الأسر في
 أيدي العلوج الغواصب فبعد سكنون
 لأن ظفرت تلك الكلاب بأكلها
 للعروق الصوارب يضرّم فيها نازه كل
 أحيان تفانى أهلها طوع فتنة حاطب
 وأضحت بها أهواؤهم وكأنا مذهبهم فيها
 واختلاف المذاهب ولم يرحم الأرحام منهم أقارب تروي سيفاً
 من نجيب أقارب
 (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

If my homeland were free, I would journey there with determination,

As though it were a necessary and purposeful mission.

But my land is now captive in the hands of impious usurpers.

How can I break its chains?

At a time when the blood in our veins has frozen,

If only I could triumph over those dogs

Who have devoured our nation—

In that place, everyone tends to their own hearth,

Yet people have fallen into a miserable state of discord.

Their hatred for one another was so intense,

It was as if they belonged to entirely different religions and sects.

No one showed mercy, not even to their own kin.

Men drew their swords and shed the blood of relatives.

In the following verses, the poet turns once more toward *madihiyyah* (panegyric). In his view, the Zirid ruler is on the righteous path—like a star shining in the sky, unwavering and steady, never repeating the errors of the rulers of Sicily.

The poet skillfully weaves the motif of longing for the homeland into the fabric of the panegyric genre: the Zirid ruler's competence and foresight are contrasted with the misguided actions of Sicily's tribal leaders. The poet elucidates the political causes behind Sicily's fall and calls upon the rulers of North Africa to learn from these lessons. In the end, the poet returns once again to the theme of longing.

أحنّ حنين النيب للموطن الذي تمنى له
 مغاني غوانيه إليه جواذي
 ومن سار عن أرض ثوى قلبه بها
 بالجسم أوبة أيب

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

I long for my homeland.

Fate draws me toward the land of beauties.

Even if you leave a place behind, your heart is buried there.

For this reason, the body always longs to return.

As we can see, the poet introduces a variety of themes within a single *qasida*. At times, he complains of the treachery of time that has distanced him from his homeland; at others, he expresses his longing for Sicily, now under enemy control. The poem includes heroic,

martial motifs and a call to arms—*tahrid* (تحريض). While the poem is essentially a eulogy, the praise of a ruler simultaneously reflects the political issues of the era. The poem recounts instructive events from Sicily's recent past and calls upon the rulers of North Africa to unite.

The poet's frequent return to Sicilian themes is, naturally, driven by a sense of longing. As he himself states, he left Sicily only physically—his heart remained in his homeland. For this reason, the body, separated from its homeland, yearns to reunite with its soul. Strikingly, despite this deep longing, the poet never once returned to Sicily, never saw his homeland again.

The theme of *nostalgia for the homeland* intensifies in Ibn Hamdis's poetry over time, as he recalls the days he spent in Sicily. His poems depicting old age also reflect this longing. N. Carpentieri writes: "Throughout his life, Ibn Hamdis maintained an emotional attachment to his native island. In many of the poems he composed in exile, the poet remembers Sicily with a sense of nostalgia and regret. In several of the poems dedicated to Sicily (*al-Siqilliyyat*), the poet contrasts his days in exile and old age with the idealized youth he experienced in Sicily" (Carpentieri, 2016).

Thus, we observe that Ibn Hamdis's poems dedicated to old age are structured around contrasts. He compares the suffering of old age with the joyful years of his youth in Sicily. The poet draws on several artistic images that have become canonical in Arabic poetry. White hair, symbolizing old age, is compared to the brightness of dawn, while black hair is associated with darkness—because the Sicily where the poet once lived his happiest days has now fallen into darkness, and Muslim rule there has come to an end. The second poem in Ibn Hamdis's *diwan* beautifully conveys these meanings.

لقد أظلمَ الشيبُ لما أضاء نَفَى هُمُ شِبْيِي سرورَ الشباب
لما تحوّلَ عَنِّي وفاءً قضيتُ لظلِّ الصبا بالزوال
ومن يجدُ الداءَ يبيغُ الدواءَ أتعرفُ لي عن شبابي سلّوا
(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

The care of white hair has replaced the joyful days of youth.

While the white hair sheds light, the world is already shrouded in darkness.

As loyalty turned its back on me, I surrendered my youth to ruin.

What solace do I have, other than to remember my youth?

One afflicted with pain seeks out a remedy.

In the following couplets, the poet speaks of the unfaithfulness of youth. In his view, youth is no more reliable than dye applied to white hair—both are deceptive and fleeting.

فأجعلُ ألكسو المشيبَ سوادَ الخضابِ
للمصبح ليلاً غطاءً وكيف أُرَجِّي وفاءَ الخضابِ
إذا لم أجدُ لشبابي وفاءً وكيف أُرَجِّي وفاءَ الخضابِ
(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

Should I apply black dye to my white hair?

Can I, by doing so, cast darkness over the face of dawn?

If youth itself has proven disloyal,

How can I expect fidelity from hair dye?

In the following verses, the poet turns to vivid imagery from nature. He describes the blowing of the soft breeze, the rain that gives life to the earth, the rumble of thunder, clouds likened to swift-running camels, and lightning flashing like a sword drawn from its sheath. The poet then juxtaposes these natural phenomena with his inner emotions, desires, and sorrows. His wishes are associated with radiant mornings and light, while his longing is evoked through images of clouds heavy with tears.

فيا غُرّةً فبتّ من الليل في ظلمة
ورويّت منه الصبح هاتي الضياء
وأريخٍ إِمّا مريّت الحيا الربوع الظماء
لأملاهنّ من الدمع ماءً فسوقي إليّ جهامَ السحابِ
فما زال في ويسقي بكائي ربع الصبا
المحل يسقى البكاء

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

In the darkness of night, I drifted into sleep.

O dawn, bring us a light.

O wind, at times you chase away the rain-filled clouds,

At times you water the thirsty earth.

Drive those abundant clouds toward us,

So we may fill them with our tears.

My tears fall for the land of my youth—

Tears still flow in that place.

Thus, in the poet's imagination, the homeland is deeply tied to tears. Just as he weeps for his homeland, so too do the people still living there cry in despair. The homeland that Ibn Hamdis mourns is not simply the Sicily he once left behind; it is a land now filled with pain and suffering. "Calamities and disasters have descended upon this land like savage beasts": (*Diwan Ibn Hamdis*, 2018).

With this poem, written in his old age, Ibn Hamdis creates vivid and evocative scenes. These scenes contain an inherent paradox. Old age is associated with the color white—white hair, in particular. White typically evokes positive feelings, reminding one of light and illumination. As the Qur'an relates in the words of Prophet Zechariah: "My hair has turned white with age..." (Surah Maryam, Verse 4).

"White hair spread a feast upon my head."

On the other hand, youth is associated with the color black due to its black hair, linked with darkness. Thus, a kind of condition arises where the poet's youthful years spent in Sicily are remembered with the color black and darkness. The poet skillfully uses all these contrasts.

It should be noted that the motif of old age and its connection to the longing for the homeland occupies an important place in Ibn Hamdis's work. Furthermore, these poems suggest that the poet lived a long life. In some of his poems, Ibn Hamdis refers to his age, and in one of the poems in his *Diwan*, he calls himself *ibn sittin* (ibn sittin) – sixty years old. In poem 30 of his *Diwan*, in one stanza, and in poem 123, he mentions being seventy years old. In another poem, he reveals that he is eighty years old.

Ibn Hamdis's "al-Siqilliyyat" poems are interesting in several respects. Along with the longing for his

homeland, one can also see the lamentation for the homeland and his native cities. On the other hand, these poems reflect the characteristics of *tahrid* (incitement) in odes. The poet lived in a time when Christian and Muslim forces were face to face. Sicily had already been lost to the Muslims. Andalusia was taking refuge under the Berber dynasties due to Christian attacks. The Berbers did not bring prosperity and stability to the country. It was not long before the Christian Reconquista movement gained strength again. Additionally, the Maghreb territories were in a constant state of war. Ibn Hamdis, a witness to all these events, wrote poems with a propagandist character. He especially calls on the people living on the border with Christians to bravery, urging them not to shy away from battle. The poet calls on his countrymen to drink the cup of death and to direct their horses to battle. His ode 270 in the Diwan is presented as follows:

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018) وقال يخاطب اهل بلده ويحرضهم على الجهاد

"Addressing the people of his own country, he calls them to jihad." The poet, who at the age of 22 left his homeland and now lives in exile, urges his fellow countrymen to bind themselves to their homeland with shackles. He believes that it is a form of happiness for people to die in their homeland, in their own village. He says, "Never fall in love with the idea of experiencing life in exile," because this life is as bitter as poison (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018).

1. The Motifs of Exile and Reminiscence in the Works of Ibn Hamdis: The motif of exile occasionally appears in poetic form throughout the poet's *diwan*. Ibn Hamdis, who once came to al-Andalus—to the court of al-Mu'tamid ibn 'Abbad in Seville—in search of a second homeland, soon found himself compelled to leave Seville as well. Within the framework of the Reconquista movement, King Alfonso VI of Castile launched successful military campaigns against Seville. He proposed to al-Mu'tamid ibn 'Abbad that he surrender by signing an agreement in which he would pay tribute. Al-Mu'tamid ibn 'Abbad... – رعى الجمال خير من رعى الخنازير – (for a muslim), herding camels is better than herding pigs for a Christian," and he calls upon Yusuf ibn Tashfin, the leader of the Berber Almoravid (Murabitun) dynasty, which had established power in North Africa, for help. Yusuf ibn Tashfin launches a successful military campaign, forcing Alfonso VI to retreat. Observing that al-Andalus had weakened due to the constant internal conflicts among its petty rulers, the Berber sovereign conquers the peninsula—including Seville—and deposes al-Mu'tamid ibn 'Abbad, imprisoning him in the Aghmat fortress in North Africa. Among the few friends who visited al-Mu'tamid during his captivity was Ibn Hamdis, who had once served as a court poet (Gasimova, 2019).

A portion of Ibn Hamdis's *Siqilliyyat* poems is constructed around the motif of reminiscence. His years spent in exile are filled with memories. He frequently recalls his homeland and its glorious past. In Qasida no. 157, Ibn Hamdis explicitly evokes this motif. The poem begins with a traditional *nasib* section. Although the

poet had never in his life seen the Arabian deserts, he adheres to classical convention by depicting the desert, camels, Bedouin desert plants, and desert maidens. It is as if the homeland he longs to reunite with and behold once more is embodied by these very deserts. The poet addresses Sicily directly, reminding it of the days gone by.

وكانت على أهل الزمان صقلية كاد الزمان بلادها
وكانت بطيب الأمن منهم فكم أعين بالخوف أمست سواها
محارسا
نواعسا

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

*Sicily! Once, in this land,
People lived in safety.*

*How many eyes stayed awake in fear.
Yet once, here, people slept in peace.*

As the poet describes his native city, Saraqusta, his sorrow deepens. He likens the Muslims who once defended the city to lions and wolves. Now, all of them have sought refuge in narrow graves. Once, the city was veiled in the smoke of ovens—now, it is engulfed in the smoke of death.

وحريرة ترمي بمخرق نبطها
فيعشى سغوط الموت فيها المعاطسا
تراهن في حمر اللبود وصفرها
كمثل بنات الزنج رقت عرايسا
إذا عثنت فيها التنايز خلتها
عنفا منافسا
تفتح للبركان

أفي قصريني رقة يعمرونها
ورسم من الإسلام أصبح دارسا
ومن عجب أن الشياطين صيرت
بروح النجوم المحرقات مجالسا
وأضحت لهم سرقوسة دار منعة
يزورون بالديرين فيا النواسا
مشتوا في بلاد أهلها تحت أرضها
وما مارسوا منهم أبيا ممارسا
ولو شقق تلك القبور لأنهضت
إليهم من الأجدات أسدا عوايسا
ولكن رأي الغيل إن غاب ليثه
تبختر في أرجائه الذئب مائسا

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

*The soldiers set this place ablaze.
The smoke of death enveloped everything.*

*The yellow and red flames of the fire were reflected in the black clouds above the city.
It was as if a dark-skinned bride had adorned herself for her wedding night.
Once, smoke would rise from the mouths of ovens that resembled volcanic craters.*

*Muslims once lived in the city of Qasriyya (Castrogiovanni),
Now, only fading traces of Islam remain in those lands.*

*It is as though devils had gathered in that place, holding a feast beneath burning stars.
Saraqusta was once as strong as a fortress.
In those times, Christians would come in groups to visit the two monasteries here;
Though they roamed these lands freely, their presence seemed reluctant.*

*If the graves here were to be torn open, grim lions would rise from them.
Now I see forests in those places, forests where no lions*

remain.

And in the absence of lions, the wolves now walk proudly.

This passage gives rise to several striking images, similes, and metaphors. By likening the black clouds hanging over the fire-ravaged city to a dark-skinned bride adorned for her wedding night, the poet creates an original and evocative simile. As the yellow and red flames of the fire reflect in the clouds, they resemble the ornaments adorning the bride.

Familiar with classical conventions and enduring poetic imagery, the poet inevitably recalls the abandoned encampment of a Bedouin Arab as he speaks of the erasure of Islam from Sicily, he evokes a deserted dwelling whose traces are gradually fading away. رسم (rasmun – literal translation: trace/remnant) and دارس (dārisun – literal translation: one who studies or fading/erased**) carry a traditional tone, evoking conventional imagery. In the *Mu‘allaqa* of Imru‘ al-Qays, the poet famously says:

“Is there anyone who does not weep at the fading traces of a deserted campsite?” - وَهَلْ عِنْدَ رَسْمِ دَارِسٍ مَنْ - مُعَوَّلٌ

The reference to devils gathering in star constellations also evokes specific associations in the poem. The poet likens the enemy to devils and the burning cities to constellations. However, the connection of devils with celestial bodies may trigger associations in the imagination of a medieval Muslim reader with certain verses from the Qur‘an, particularly those found in Surah al-Jinn, verses 8–9.

Likewise, the image of graves being opened evokes eschatological imagery related to the Islamic concept of the Day of Resurrection (*Yawm al-Hashr*). Thus, we observe how the literary heritage of regions in direct contact with the Christian world remains profoundly linked to the broader cultural and intellectual legacy of the Muslim empire. Both the poetic tradition and Islamic worldview are vividly reflected here.

As N. Carpentieri rightly notes, the works of Ibn Hamdis demonstrate his deep familiarity with the Arabic poetic canon and the linguistic sciences—something that could only have been achieved through a high level of formal education (Carpentieri, 2016).

The motif of longing in Ibn Hamdis’s poetry reveals significant genre versatility. These poems may be seen as elegies (*marthiyyāt*) composed in memory of his lost homeland (Toprak, 1999). Elements of elegy expressing the pain of exile also appear in panegyrics, laudatory poetry, ghazals, and *khamriyyāt* (wine poems). Whenever the poet dedicates a poem to someone from Sicily, memories of his homeland and the youthful years spent there resurface. In a panegyric dedicated to the commander Muhibb ibn ‘Abd al-Ḥakam al-Siqillī, the poet writes:

وأنا الفاقد ريعان الشباب
كيف لا أبكي بهذا كله
كان ما بين الشبيهين
صدت البيض عن البيض أما
انجذاب

الماء لظمانٍ سراب
أفلا أبكي شباباً فقدته قلب

لو رماها خدقاتٍ لأصاب
أخطأ الشيب ظباءً، والصبأ

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

How can I not weep? I have lost my youth.

The whiteness (of my hair) reminds me of bright days past—

Things that resemble each other are naturally drawn together.

Do I not weep for the youth I have lost?

I am like a man scorched by thirst, who sees water in a mirage.

Like white hair mistakenly seen on a gazelle—

The stones thrown at it miss their mark.

As we can see, the poet weaves elements of elegy (*marthiya*) into the structure of the panegyric, creating a syncretic genre. He first and foremost mourns his past—his youth, his white hair. The homeland he has lost is as distant as his bygone youth, unreachable like a mirage.

As previously noted, the motif of exile in Ibn Hamdis’s poetry is treated with considerable genre flexibility. Just as he explores it in elegies and panegyrics, he also connects the theme of exile to his *khamriyyāt* (wine poetry), descriptive poems (*waṣf*), and ghazals. Each genre provides its own transitional pathway to express this theme. The *khamriyyāt* and ghazals, in particular, bring back memories of youth, inevitably leading the poet to recall Sicily.

Though Ibn Hamdis remains deeply attached to Sicily, he no longer longs to return to his old life. In his eyes, Sicily is a symbol of youth. Now in his old age, the poet is no longer drawn to pleasures or wine.

إلى لهو، فرغت من الشباب فلست أرو
فيشغلني الرحيق
أفتلذمني ولا أنا في صقلية غلام
لكل هوى حقوق

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

I am no longer young. Amusements no longer attract me.

I do not need old wine.

I am no longer the young man I once was in Sicily.

Now, I have worries of my own.

Everyone originally from Sicily holds a special place in the poet’s heart. The death of fellow Sicilians causes him particular grief. He dedicates an elegy to a Sicilian named ‘Abd al-Ghani ibn ‘Abd al-‘Aziz (Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018). From this elegy, it becomes clear that the deceased’s father was a prominent military commander. The elegy begins with the traditional *dahr* motif—complaining of time’s cruelty. The poet laments that *dahr* (fate or time) is especially merciless toward loyal and virtuous individuals.

However, in the house of the grave, valiant commanders, cowards, and the misguided are indistinguishable. Though these individuals experienced vastly different circumstances in life, they all stand powerless before the treachery and deceit of time.

وهي تشحو بالجانب
كيف تنجو على مطية دنيا
الوحشي
وركوب
تطرح الراكب الشديد سموسا
السموس فعل صفي

(Diwan Ibn Hamdis, 2018)

How can one escape the camel called the world?

It strides forward like a wild beast—dangerously.

Even the strongest rider is easily thrown to the ground.

Mounting an unbroken camel is the act of a fool.

Professor A. Gasimova compares this image of *dahr* (time/fate) to the figure of Fortuna, the goddess of fate in Greek mythology (Gasimova, 2014).

Conclusion: The motif of longing for Sicily is reflected in many genres of Ibn Hamdis's poetry. Regardless of the genre, the poet skillfully brings the theme of exile to the forefront. The genres of *khamriyyah* and *ghazal* remind him of his youth and the happy days he spent in Sicily. The depiction of old age and gray hair... – (شيب) The motif of *shayb* (gray hair) evokes memories of youth as a contrast to a sorrowful state, once again resonating with notes of longing for the homeland. The praise of the rulers of al-Andalus and North Africa serves as a basis for recalling the tribal rulers of Sicily. The poet calls upon these rulers to unite against a common enemy. *Tahrid* (incitement to action or encouragement for unity)... (تحريض) characterizes this poem, in which the *hamasah* (حماسة – heroism) genre also functions as an integral component. On the other hand, Ibn

Hamdis allocates space to the motif of exile in his elegiac poetry. The estrangement of both the deceased who die in exile and their graves adds a poignant sorrow to the elegy genre. In all cases, Ibn Hamdis appears as a poet of Sicily.

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